

Multi-Attribute Decision Making-based Trust Score Calculation in Trust Management in IoT

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ABSTRACT

The proliferation of IoT networks across various sectors necessitates robust Trust Management mechanisms for secure and reliable operations. This paper proposes a Multi-Attribute Decision Making (MADM)-based approach for trust score calculation in IoT Trust Management. This solution addresses limitations of existing methods by considering multiple attributes and providing a comprehensive evaluation of trustworthiness. The methodology computes a device's trust score by integrating factors such as Cyber Risk, Ease of Access, and Security Level using a weighted sum-based calculation. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) to determine the factors' weights is utilized, contributing a novel approach to IoT Trust Management. Furthermore, this approach includes dynamic trust score updates throughout the device's lifetime, accommodating changes in the device's Cyber Risk for accurate trust assessment. A trust score penalization mechanism for devices below a predefined threshold is also introduced, enabling prompt risk mitigation. A simulated assessment, considering varying numbers of IoT devices, evaluates the effectiveness of the proposed methodology. By addressing limitations and introducing innovative components, the proposed MADM-based approach enhances security, reliability, and overall performance of IoT networks. This research advances trust management in IoT and provides valuable insights for developing secure and trustworthy IoT ecosystems.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Security and privacy; • Systems security;

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KEYWORDS

IoT, Trust Management, Distributed Ledger Technologies, IoT networks

1 INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized various domains of everyday life, encompassing critical sectors such as Industry 4.0, transportation, utilities, and healthcare. The proliferation of IoT networks has enabled seamless connectivity and interaction among a vast array of devices, facilitating the exchange of data and the delivery of services [22]. However, ensuring the secure and efficient operation of IoT devices and networks remains a significant challenge [23]. IoT networks consist of heterogeneous devices with diverse software and hardware configurations, often manufactured by different vendors. This heterogeneity introduces complexities in establishing trust relationships among the devices, as they need to cooperate and provide reliable services to one another.

In the context of IoT networks, trust implies that a device (Service Provider) will reliably provide accurate services to another (Service Requester). Trust Management (TM) methods offer potential solutions to issues surrounding this trust, by assessing the trustworthiness of devices and fostering trust relationships within the network. This helps improve network security, reliability, and performance [24]. However, current TM methods often utilize oversimplified trust models that overlook various factors, such as the initial trust score of a device, which is key to determining its trustworthiness. They also fail to account for the dynamic nature of trust, neglecting to update the device's trust score over time or penalize untrustworthy behavior, risking the network's overall trustworthiness. This paper proposes a comprehensive framework that addresses these limitations using a Multi-Attribute Decision Making (MADM)-based approach for calculating trust scores in IoT's TM. The approach aims to enhance trust evaluation accuracy and help IoT devices make informed decisions on trust relationships.

By considering multiple attributes, the MADM solution strives to improve overall network trustworthiness. Typically, MADM is applied as a weighted sum or average function to evaluate alternatives [29].

Our proposed solution represents a significant advancement in IoT device trust score computation. We introduce a dynamic methodology that calculates these scores over multiple time periods, reflecting the devices' evolving conditions and behaviors. This holistic evaluation considers three crucial factors: Cyber Risk, Ease of Access, and Security Level, thereby providing a comprehensive assessment of trust.

To determine the weights for these factors in the trust score function, we utilize the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)—a well-established method for tackling complex decisions. This application of AHP presents a notable contribution to the field of IoT trust management. To the best of our knowledge, this innovative use of AHP is unique, underscoring the novelty of our approach.

Furthermore, our method calculates not only the initial trust score but also those specific to each epoch, facilitating continuous trust evaluation. This dynamic approach addresses the limitations inherent in static trust evaluations, yielding a more robust measure of device trustworthiness.

Additionally, our solution introduces an unprecedented penalty mechanism for devices exceeding a predefined Cyber Risk threshold, thereby bolstering network security and reliability. The proposed solution's efficacy is corroborated through comprehensive simulation evaluations across diverse network scenarios, providing valuable insights into its practical applicability. Collectively, these contributions endorse our proposed solution as an innovative and instrumental framework for IoT network trust management.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the related work for TM in IoT and the methods used to calculate a device's trust score along with the considered parameters. Section 3 presents the architecture of the proposed solution, along with its components and the sequence of operations. Section 4 presents the adversary and threat model along with the security assumptions of the proposed solution as well as the means to defend against these threats. Finally, Section 5 gives insight into the performance of the proposed TM scheme while Section 6 concludes the paper and outlines future work.

2 RELATED WORK

This literature review examines significant studies in TM within IoT networks, focusing on device-related criteria such as Quality of Service, Delays, and service feedback. It aims to identify and critique the key methodologies for calculating a device's trust score. The review bifurcates into two categories: Blockchain-based and non-blockchain-based TM approaches.

2.1 Blockchain-based Trust Management

The authors of [4] propose a blockchain-based method for establishing IoT device trust in supply chains, considering both direct and indirect trust, with trust scores being determined based on historical feedback and recommendations. In a similar vein, [5] outlines a scalable blockchain-based solution for key and TM in IoT networks, emphasizing the device's reputation and feedback from

past experiences. Transitioning to vehicular networks, [6] introduces a blockchain-based TM model for Vehicular Ad-hoc Networks (VANETs). This model leverages the Hyperledger Fabric blockchain, and trust scores are calculated using a Hidden Markov Model that factors in historical vehicle behavior and message authenticity.

On another front, [7] describes a blockchain-based TM model specifically designed for agricultural green supply chains, utilizing a game theory model based on the Bayesian formula. This model generates trust scores from positive and negative sensor feedback. [8] shifts focus to smart buildings, presenting a blockchain-based TM mechanism that evaluates device trustworthiness as a weighted sum of past and current trust values. Diversifying the application further, [9] proposes a TM methodology combining blockchain technology and fog computing, which considers service-specific parameters when calculating a device's trust score. Expanding on these principles, [10] offers a blockchain-based TM model in IoT that amalgamates direct and indirect trust information, employing a decay function and adaptable weights for dynamic trust value calculations.

In the context of distributed ledger technology, [12] lays out an identity and trust framework for IoT devices, where trust relationships are expressed as graph edges. Taking a different approach, [15] proposes a TM methodology that computes an initial trust score for an IoT device by considering an array of factors, including the remote attestation outcome, the device owner, the application context, and computational resources. Finally, [30] explores the use of an alliance blockchain to compute an IoT device's trust score, utilizing a weighted sum function that factors in the device's reputation and other feature scores, bringing us full circle to the trust considerations highlighted in the earliest works.

2.2 Non Blockchain-based Trust Management

The authors in [1] suggest a Trust Management (TM) approach that calculates an IoT device's trust score considering attributes like Quality of Service, Availability, Cruciality, Responsiveness, and Cooperation. In [2], a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) approach with Deep Long Short-Term Memory Technique is employed to calculate the device's trust score, with parameters like Packet Loss, Delay, and Throughput considered. They use Shannon's entropy function to determine the weights of each input. The paper [3] proposes a context-dependent TM technique for job selection and allocation in a Social IoT environment, considering factors such as the device's Capabilities, its commitment, and consumer satisfaction. In [11], the authors treat the IoT network as a graph representing trust relationships between devices, with trust formed through a random-walk network exploration algorithm. In [13], an Edge-Based TM system for smart cities is proposed, factoring in both direct and indirect trust. The trust score is determined by events related to the devices. The work in [14] presents EdgeTrust, a TM model addressing good-mouthing and bad-mouthing attacks, considering Direct Trust, Indirect Trust, and Past experience for trust score calculation. In [16], a hybrid TM scheme for the Internet of Vehicles (IoV) is proposed, evaluating both the information's authenticity and its source. Finally, [17] presents a hybrid trust computation scheme relying on Bayesian learning and Dempster-Shafer Theory (DST) for data fusion and trustworthiness computation.

The studies detailed in subsections 2.1 and 2.2 have several limitations, notably their inattention to the initial trust score of IoT devices. Most assign an arbitrary low value, which can be misleading and unfair. One approach [15] computes an initial score using certain device parameters, but it does not update this score throughout the device's lifecycle. Moreover, the parameters used aren't highly relevant to a device's trustworthiness, and no method for penalizing malicious behavior is suggested. This paper addresses these shortcomings by proposing a methodology to calculate initial and updated trust scores considering the device's Cyber Risk, Ease of Access, and Security Level. It also introduces a mechanism to penalize malicious devices by reducing their trust scores.

3 SOLUTION DESCRIPTION

3.1 System Architecture

The proposed Trust Management (TM) model consists of four elements: a) The Trust Manager and Broker (TMB), b) Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), c) IoT devices, and d) Trust Score Calculation Methodology.

The TMB, a critical element with substantial computational and communication resources, manages multiple IoT device requests and trustworthiness evaluations. Trustworthiness factors include a device's Cyber Risk, Ease of Access, and Security Level. Additionally, the TMB hosts and runs the Slow Start and Fast Recovery Trust Score calculation algorithms and maintains network IoT devices' trust history. TMBs are inherently trusted and multiple TMBs are operational within an IoT network to avoid single-point failures.

DLT provides immutable, consistently accessible trust records for devices, preventing single-point failures and unauthorized trust data alteration. Smart contracts manage the storage and retrieval of information on the DLT, with distinct access permissions for each stakeholder. Specifically, only the TMB can write and retrieve trust data, while IoT devices and Service Requesters (SRs) can only read data. Trust history is preserved on the DLT, even post network exit. The preferred DLT for this architecture is consortium Hyperledger Fabric [27].

The proposed Trust Management approach centers around IoT devices, which are subjected to regular trustworthiness evaluations. While most devices have limited computational capabilities, some, like the Raspberry Pi 4 [31], possess higher resources, allowing for more robust security mechanisms. Each device, which can function as both a Service Provider and a Service Requester (SR), is assigned credentials to interact with the DLT.

The Trust Score Calculation methodology assesses device trustworthiness under two scenarios. In high Cyber Risk situations, indicative of low trustworthiness and potential service failures, devices receive low trust scores that gradually increase, to avoid service disruptions. Specifically, a device with high Cyber Risk is penalized with a zero-trust score for two epochs before its trust score incrementally increases every two epochs. In contrast, in low Cyber Risk circumstances, the device's trust score is determined by its security parameters, and it's penalized with a zero-trust score only in epochs with high associated risks.

The solution's operational flow starts with the device joining the network and sharing its Security Level and Ease of Access data with the Trust Manager and Broker (TMB). The TMB assesses the

Figure 1: Solution's Architectural components and sequence of operation

device's Cyber Risk and interprets the received data. Depending on the network's overall Cyber Risk, it applies the appropriate trust score calculation algorithm (SSTS or FRTS) using the interpreted data. Upon calculation completion, the trust score is recorded to the DLT via chaincode functions, and then communicated to the device. If an SR wishes to use the device's services, they can access its trustworthiness information from the DLT. This process repeats every epoch, as shown in Figure 1, which illustrates the interactions among architecture components.

3.2 The trust score calculation mechanism

This section describes the proposed trust algorithm and its functionalities. More specifically it outlines its sequence of operations, the variables it receives as inputs, how it rewards and penalizes devices, and the way a device's trust score is calculated.

The device attributes the trust score calculation algorithm considers are the Cyber Risk regarding that device, the Ease of Access to the device, and the Device's Security Level. The device's Cyber Risk indicates the likelihood of this device failing to provide correct service and/or being compromised and has values in the range [1,100]. However, when the algorithm uses it, Cyber Risk is normalized in the range [0,1]. The Ease of Access attribute indicates how easy it is to access the device and tamper physically or remotely with it. This attribute is binary and takes values 0 and 1 with 0 indicating no Ease of Access and 1 indicating high Ease of Access. The device's Security Level takes values from the vector [0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1]. This attribute indicates the level of security this device currently attains in terms of software updates or/and security tools it utilizes (e.g., firewall, antivirus) and whether the device has a cryptoprocessor (e.g., TPM, SGX, or TEE). The closer the Security Level is to 0.25 the lower the security capabilities of the device while the closer to 1 the higher they are. The trust score of a device is calculated as the weighted sum of the values corresponding to the above attributes in each epoch. Specifically, the equation used to calculate a device's trust score is given by equation 1).

$$TS = w_1 * A_1 + w_2 * A_2 + w_3 * A_3 \quad (1)$$

A_1 , A_2 , A_3 are the device's Cyber Risk, the Ease of Access to the device and the device's Security level respectively. The weights ($w_1 + w_2 + w_3 = 1$) corresponding to these attributes are produced

through the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) [25] method and indicate the significance of each attribute to the trust score.

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), a popular Multi-Attribute Decision Making method, structures decision problems hierarchically with numerous elements. These elements are pairwise compared to ascertain their relative importance, using a Pairwise Comparison matrix, with elements graded from 1 to 9. A grade of 1 implies equal importance, while 9 denotes extreme importance. In this study, each matrix attribute corresponds to an attribute in the device's trust score calculation algorithm. They are pairwise compared within a square matrix (NxN) based on their influence on trust score calculation, with 'N' being the number of attributes used in the calculation. Matrix elements can assume values between 1 and 9, denoting their significance level.

- $element_{i,j} = 1$: when a parameter is compared with itself and consequently has equal importance. Additionally, this value can also signify that two parameters i and j have equal importance.
- $element_{i,j} > 1$: when parameter i is more important than parameter j
- $element_{i,j} < 1$: when parameter i is less important than parameter j
- $element_{i,j} = 1/element_{j,i}$: a fraction that signifies an intermediate level of importance.

To compute the weight of each parameter the pairwise matrix is normalized in the range $[0,1]$. Then by calculating the geometric mean on the normalized matrix the priority vector [26] is produced which has a size of $1 \times N$. The elements of this vector are the weights of the parameters used in the trust score calculation algorithm while the sum of these weights is equal to 1. To verify that all AHP related computations and comparisons have been performed correctly the consistency ratio of the normalized pairwise comparison matrix is computed. If the consistency ratio is lesser than 0.1 then the pairwise comparison matrix is deemed consistent which is the case here. The values of these weights in (1) are $w_1 = 0.0833$, $w_2 = 0.3333$ and $w_3 = 0.5833$.

In this study, the Cyber Risk and Ease of Access attributes negatively influence a device's trust score, while the Security Level attribute impacts positively. Thus, the proposed solution assigns negative signs to the former in the weighted sum function. The proposed trust score calculation methodology offers two versions: the Slow Start Trust Score (SSTS) calculation and the Fast Recovery Trust Score (FRTS) calculation, each addressing specific scenarios.

The SSTS algorithm (Algorithm 1) is suitable for IoT networks facing multiple untrustworthy devices and cyber threats. These devices offer malicious or faulty services, potentially causing significant damage to the IoT-enabled ecosystem and application domains, like smart transportation. To avoid system failure or severe damage, services from these compromised IoT devices must be circumvented. If a device's Cyber Risk score exceeds a certain threshold, suggesting danger, its trust score is reduced to 0 for the current and following epoch. This deters prospective Service Requesters from using such damaging devices. Regardless of the calculated trust score in the next epoch, the SSTS algorithm will gradually increase the device's trust score every two epochs if the network or devices still have high Cyber Risk.

The FRTS algorithm (Algorithm 2), on the other hand, works best in IoT networks where devices are generally trustworthy and offer high-quality, honest services. While these devices may occasionally fail due to malicious actions or accidental errors, the likelihood is low, resulting in inherently low Cyber Risk. In such cases, a device's trust score should reflect changes in any of the three parameters. A high Security Level and low Cyber Risk and Ease of Access values lead to a high trust score. However, if a device's Cyber Risk exceeds a threshold, its trust score is set to 0, indicating complete distrust, akin to the SSTS algorithm. The key distinction between SSTS and FRTS is that once Cyber Risk falls below the threshold, FRTS reassigns the calculated trust score in the current epoch, regardless of any previous penalization.

The FRTS algorithm employs the same attributes, weights, signs, and signed weights as SSTS but with a different sequence of operations. Initially, the device's trust score is calculated like in SSTS, resulting in a real number between 0 and 1. Then, if the device's Cyber Risk surpasses a 0.5 threshold, the trust score is reduced to 0 for this epoch. However, if it remains below this threshold, the original trust score is preserved, but negative trust scores are set to 0. Both algorithms start with trust score calculation, but if malicious behavior is detected, the flow of Algorithm 1 is followed.

Algorithm 1 Slow Start Trust Score calculation.

Inputs

devRisk A device's Cyber Risk
 devEA A device's Ease of Access
 devSecLvl A device's Security Level
 weights[] The criteria weights
 weightsSigns[] The criteria weights signs
 threshold A predefined value in the range $[0, 1]$
 increment A real number in the range $[0, 1]$

Outputs

trustScore A device's trust score

Begin

```
signedWeights ← weights*weightsSigns /*Vector with signed weights*/
trustScore ← devRisk*signedWeights[1] +
devEA*signedWeights[2] + devSecLvl*signedWeights[3]
if (devRisk > threshold) then /*The device is penalized with negative trust score*/
    trustScore ← 0
else if (devRisk < threshold && trustScore(previousEpoch) = 0)
then
    //Do the following calculation in the current
epoch
    trustScore ← trustScore + increment
//In the next epoch do the following assignment
    trustScore ← trustScore(previousEpoch)
end if
end
```

Algorithm 2 Fast Recovery Trust Score calculation**Inputs**

devRisk A device's Cyber Risk

devEA A device's Ease of Access

devSecLvl A device's Security Level

weights[] The criteria weights

weightsSigns[] The criteria weights signs

threshold A predefined value in the range [0, 1]

Outputs

trustScore A device's trust score

beginsignedWeights \leftarrow weights*weightsSigns /*Vector with signed weights*/

```

trustScore  $\leftarrow$  devRisk*signedWeights[1] +
devEA*signedWeights[2] + devSecLvl*signedWeights[3]
if (devRisk > threshold then /*The device is penalized with
negative trust score*/

```

```

    trustScore  $\leftarrow$  0

```

```

else if (devRisk < threshold) then /*The device's trust score takes
the value from the weighted sum function.*/

```

```

    trustScore  $\leftarrow$  trustScore

```

end if

end

4 SECURITY CONSIDERATIONS AND PROPOSED SOLUTIONS

This section outlines the proposed method's security model, countermeasures, and potential threats. The primary cyber threat addressed by this Trust Management (TM) approach is harmful attacks or actions that could compromise an IoT device, causing it to deliver substandard service. This could disrupt an application's IoT ecosystem, potentially leading to significant failures if services from a compromised device are utilized.

In response, the Trust Manager and Broker (TMB) assesses specific aspects of the IoT network to determine the overall Cyber Risk. If the Cyber Risk is deemed too high, the TMB implements the SSTS algorithm to calculate a device's trust score. Should the associated Cyber Risk surpass a certain threshold, as determined by Algorithm 1, the device's trust score is set to 0, irrespective of the output from the weighted sum function. This occurs as the SSTS algorithm deems a device with such high Cyber Risk as compromised. It is therefore not chosen as a Service Provider while its Cyber Risk remains high, mitigating potential damage to the IoT ecosystem and the applications relying on it, including critical infrastructures like smart transportation or energy.

When the Cyber Risk falls below the threshold, the device's trust score is incrementally increased every two epochs. Despite a potentially higher value calculated by the MADM weighted sum function, it would be inaccurate to assume this score accurately reflects the device's trustworthiness, especially if part of a high-risk IoT network. Rapidly assigning a high trust score in the immediate next epoch would be unrealistic.

The SSTS algorithm not only shields Service Requesters from faulty services and protects the IoT ecosystem, but it also incentivizes Service Providers in high-risk IoT networks to improve their security measures. Notably, once a device's trust score plummets

to 0, it requires considerable time to reach a score above 0.5. Thus, device owners are encouraged to prevent attacks and actions that would increase their IoT devices' Cyber Risk. This approach enhances their devices' trust scores, likelihood of being chosen as service providers, and the overall cybersecurity stance of the IoT network.

TM-specific attacks such as good-mouthing, bad-mouthing, and other forms of attacks [18, 19, 20, 21] are not part of the current threat and adversary model and are beyond the scope of this work.

5 PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

5.1 Experimental setup

To evaluate Algorithms 1 and 2 the authors implemented them using the Octave [28] programming language version 8.1.0. The reason for choosing Octave is the fact that it supports complex algebraic calculations and the generation of various probability distributions with ready built-in functions. As mentioned in Section 3 the proposed algorithms calculate the trust score of one or more devices for multiple epochs. To simulate these epochs "for loops" were utilized with each iteration in the loop representing an epoch. To evaluate the performance of the algorithms, values corresponding to the device's Cyber Risk, Ease of Access, and Security Level attributes were necessary. To this end, the authors used Octave built-in functions to generate them. To model a device's Cyber Risk attribute a log normal distribution was used. That means that the Cyber Risk value of a device follows a log-normal distribution curve. To simulate the fact a device's Cyber Risk may change between epochs, the implementation randomly selects in each epoch a value from the Cyber Risk log-normal distribution curve. The implementation randomly chooses a value from the vector [0.25 0.5 0.75 1] to generate the Security Level attribute in an epoch for a device. Regarding the Ease of Access attribute, the implementation generates it by randomly choosing in each epoch between the integer values 0 and 1. These randomly selected values are used as inputs in the weighted sum function to calculate a device's trust score for an epoch.

5.2 Results and Discussions

The implementations of both Algorithms 1 and 2 were tested on a desktop running Windows 10 equipped with an AMD Ryzen 5 3600 6-Core Processor CPU, 16GB of RAM, and a 500GB SSD drive. To evaluate the behavior of the algorithms three scenarios were implemented and tested for both the SSTS and FRTS. Specifically, these scenarios involved testing the algorithms for different numbers of devices and different Cyber Risk values.

The key variation in these scenarios lies in the region of the log-normal distribution where the Cyber Risk exceeds 0.5 and the number of IoT devices in each scenario. This region is defined by the log-normal distribution's standard deviation value, set as 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1 for each scenario. Figure 4 depicts how different standard deviation values of the log-normal distribution affect the Cyber Risk curve. The Cyber Risk tied to a device surpasses the threshold value (0.5) in 30%, 55%, 75%, and 88% of all values in a log-normal distribution Cyber Risk curve for corresponding standard deviations of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1. This results in the device's trust

Table 1: Average Trust score calculated for different scenarios (i.e., IoT network size) and cybersecurity risk for the Slow Start Trust Score Calculation algorithm.

Scenario Risk	Mean Value = 1.0317 Variance = 0.068654 ($\mu = 0 \sigma = 0.25$)	Mean Value=1.3248 Variance= 1.3252 ($\mu = 0 \sigma = 0.75$)	Mean Value = 1.3248 Variance = 1.3252 ($\mu = 0 \sigma = 0.75$)	Mean Value = 1.6487 Variance = 4.6708 ($\mu = 0 \sigma = 1$)
S1 (5 dev)	0.1255	0.050384	0.015703	3.8614e-03
S2 (10 dev)	0.1272	0.049765	0.015089	4.4156e-03
S3 (20 dev)	0.1229	0.049614	0.015955	4.0812e-03

Table 2: Average Trust score calculated for different scenarios (i.e., IoT network size) and cybersecurity risk for the Fast Recovery Trust Score Calculation algorithm.

Scenario Risk	Mean Value = 1.0317 Variance = 0.068654 ($\mu = 0 \sigma = 0.25$)	Mean Value=1.3248 Variance = 1.3252 ($\mu = 0 \sigma = 0.75$)	Mean Value = 1.3248 Variance = 1.3252 ($\mu = 0 \sigma = 0.75$)	Mean Value = 1.6487 Variance= 4.6708 ($\mu = 0 \sigma = 1$)
S1 (5 dev)	0.1633	0.011793	0.045594	0.023603
S2 (10 dev)	0.1696	0.1045	0.020800	0.026174
S3 (20 dev)	0.1499	0.043024	0.022125	0.027355

Figure 2: Bar chart for average trust score in the Slow Start Trust Score calculation algorithm

score being set to 0 for 30, 55, 75, and 88 out of 100 epochs for each respective standard deviation.

In these scenarios, the average trust score in the network over 100 epochs was calculated for Algorithms 1 and 2. Table 1 and the bar chart in Figure 2 display the results for each scenario, considering varying device numbers and standard deviations in the log-normal risk curve. The findings confirm that the device's associated Cyber Risk in Algorithm 1 has a greater impact on the device's trust score than the values of the device's Ease of Access and Security Level parameters. Furthermore, as evidenced by each table column, the number of devices in each scenario doesn't impact the trust score of each device, and hence, doesn't affect the network's average trust score. As the standard deviation of the log-normal distribution curve representing the devices' Cyber Risk increases, the average device trust score decreases, indicating an inverse relationship between Cyber Risk and the device's trust score. Figure 2's bar chart visually represents the average trust score for each scenario, with the blue,

Figure 3: Bar chart for average trust score in the Fast Recovery Trust Score calculation algorithm

orange, yellow, and blue bars signifying the average trust score for a standard deviation of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1, respectively.

In assessing Algorithm 2, the results confirm that risk continues to influence the device's trust score and, consequently, the network's average trust score across all epochs. Nonetheless, as indicated by the data in Table 2 and Figure 3, the device's trust score is not heavily affected by the Cyber Risk value. When risk falls below the threshold, parameters such as Ease of Access and Security Level also contribute to the trust score formation. This variation can be attributed to the distinct operation of Algorithm 2

Table 2 illustrates that the distribution of average trust scores under the FRTS approach, for various standard deviations, does not mirror the distribution observed with the SSTS approach. Figure 3, which displays the average trust score for each scenario, reinforces this finding. The blue, orange, yellow, and purple bars correspond to standard deviations of 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, and 1, respectively. This discrepancy arises because FRTS does not bind the trust score value

Figure 4: Normalized Cyber Risk curves for standard deviation values equal to 0.25, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.

tightly to the Cyber Risk value. Consequently, trust scores may fluctuate in each epoch. This fluctuation mainly occurs because the trust score, under FRTS, is determined by the weighted sum function in every epoch where the device's Cyber Risk is below a specified threshold. In contrast, Algorithm 1 only increases the trust score steadily every two epochs, but only after the Cyber Risk falls below the threshold.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper introduced a new methodology for computing Trust Scores in IoT Trust Management, employing Multi-Attribute Decision Making (MADM) to calculate an IoT device's trust score throughout its network lifespan. The proposed method offers two computation perspectives: one for devices within a high cybersecurity risk IoT network (SSTS), and another for devices in networks with comparatively low Cyber Risk (FRTS).

Evaluation results of Algorithm 1 reveal a strong correlation between an IoT device's trust score and its associated Cyber Risk, with MADM function results disregarded when risk surpasses a certain threshold. In contrast, results from the FRTS algorithm confirm that the trust score it generates is not strongly tied to the device's associated Cyber Risk in each epoch and can accept the value from the trust score calculation function.

Future research will involve testing the SSTS and FRTS algorithms within a dynamic IoT network simulation where devices frequently enter and leave. Further developments include the use of a more efficient, less resource-intensive language to enhance the algorithm's performance and decrease the time taken to compute a device's trust score. The potential for trust-related attacks against these proposed algorithms will also be examined, and appropriate defense mechanisms will be integrated.

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